
Moderating effect of capital structure on the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and firm performance: Evidence from GCC

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of corporate governance mechanisms on firm performance in Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries, with a focus on the moderating role of capital structure. Using panel data from 133 non-financial listed firms across five GCC countries over the period 2016–2023, the analysis employs the two-step System Generalized Method of Moments (System GMM) to address potential endogeneity and unobserved heterogeneity. The results show that CEO duality has a negative and statistically significant effect on both return on assets (ROA) and Tobin's Q, consistent with agency theory. Board size is positively associated with firm value, whereas institutional ownership is positively associated with profitability. The interaction between leverage and CEO duality is significant and differs across models: leverage intensifies the adverse effect of CEO duality on profitability (ROA). However, it mitigates its negative impact on market valuation (Tobin's Q). This study is among the first to examine the moderating role of capital structure on the corporate governance–firm performance relationship in the GCC context. It contributes to the literature by integrating agency theory and resource

dependence theory within a unique institutional environment and providing evidence from an emerging-market perspective.

Keywords: Corporate governance, Firm performance, GCC, Capital structure, Agency theory.

How to Cite: Faiza Abdalla Sheikh Batoun, Rosli Mahmood. (2026). Moderating effect of capital structure on the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and firm performance: Evidence from GCC. *International Journal of Finance (IJFIN)*, 39(1), 45–73.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18754519>

1. INTRODUCTION

Corporate governance, as defined by the Cadbury, (1992)The system that directs and controls companies. It provides a framework for managing diverse stakeholders' interests in an open, responsible, and ethical manner. Corporate governance is the process by which companies' financial providers ensure that their investments will yield a profit (Shleifer and Vishny, 1997). Corporate governance provides a framework for setting goals and monitoring performance. It encompasses the interactions among a company's shareholders, board of directors, management, and other stakeholders. To ensure accountability, equity, and transparency, corporate governance (CG) is an essential component of company operations. Therefore, it might also be used to describe stakeholder relationships and the goals the business must meet (Çelik and Isaksson, 2014).A sound corporate governance structure promotes ethical business practices and optimizes resource allocation, potentially lowering capital expenditures, improving firm performance, and sustaining wealth creation for shareholders (Tawfik et al., 2022). In the GCC, awareness of good governance only emerged as a significant and contentious topic around the start of the twenty-first century. Gulf authorities began implementing many CG reforms with support from the International Finance Corporation, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, and other independent and international organizations. Thus, Oman's 2002 publication of its CG code marked the beginning of the first wave of CG practices in the GCC, which was followed by the UAE in 2004, the KSA in 2006, Qatar in 2009, Bahrain in 2010, and Kuwait in 2013 (Abdallah & Ismail, 2017; Salman & Nobanee, 2019).

GCC's oil earnings have historically dominated the region, accelerating its wealth and development. The reduction in oil earnings has led GCC nations to face governance and stability challenges, exacerbated by their growing populations and traditional income-based social contracts. Each GCC nation is aggressively pursuing economic diversification by reducing dependence on oil and boosting private-sector involvement. As a result, national plans include opening the economy, building knowledge-based industries, and reducing reliance on oil. In the face of intense competition, these diversification initiatives emphasize sectors such as software and technology, banking, and tourism, given their potential for substantial productivity gains and employment growth. The GCC states are addressing the problems of economic diversification to reduce dependence on oil income and foster sustainable economic growth. Therefore, diversification efforts will be further supported by the recent change in GCC investments toward clean energy and renewable projects. To further attract international investment and improve the investment climate, the GCC nations have begun reforming their laws, streamlining procedures, and establishing specialized agencies (Korniyenko and Xin, 2025). Therefore, corporate governance is crucial to financial markets, as it ensures that businesses operate responsibly and transparently. In addition to boosting investor confidence and balancing the interests of multiple stakeholders, effective corporate governance practices may increase market capitalization and enhance financial performance. This feature is particularly crucial in the GCC, where financial markets are expanding dramatically as part of the region's attempts to diversify its economy (Bai et al., 2023).

Despite notable advancements in corporate governance frameworks across the GCC, these measures aim to reduce agency costs. Assessing their effect on company performance alone will always yield an inadequate conclusion, because a complex interplay of internal and external factors shapes firm performance. This is because businesses exist to generate wealth for their shareholders, and maximizing shareholder wealth requires funding growth-oriented, value-enhancing, long-term initiatives and acquisitions. Funding is occasionally necessary for such significant growth expenditures. Hence, leverage is crucial in the firm's pursuit of maximizing shareholder value. Indeed, although the crucial role of capital structure choices, such as debt maturity and leverage levels, in affecting company performance and reducing agency costs (Jensen, 1986) is well established, their efficacy often depends on the standard of corporate governance. Theoretically, increased debt might discipline managers by decreasing free cash flow and enhancing creditor oversight (Jensen & Meckling, 1976).

The ideal mix of debt and equity ratios is known as the optimal capital structure. Because interest is a tax-deductible expense, a company should choose the optimal capital structure. On the other hand, financial difficulties may result from companies becoming overly indebted. Corporate financing decisions are crucial in an organization's corporate system. Any decisions made by the company's board could affect the financial leverage policy. Successful business operations require well-defined, documented policies and processes. Consequently, company failures and increased business complexity have necessitated stronger corporate governance. The lack of good corporate governance may have significant implications for national economies. A corporation may face a financial crisis if its debt load exceeds an optimal level and it fails to adhere to sound corporate governance practices. Economic crises, major corporate scandals, and unexpected corporate collapses have heightened awareness of the need for robust corporate governance to prevent such risks (Puni & Anlesinya, 2020). Although both corporate governance systems and capital structure decisions serve as tools to reduce agency costs, it remains unclear which mechanism is more prevalent in the GCC setting. To address this gap, this study will examine the impact of corporate governance on firm performance. In addition, we examine the interaction effects of leverage with each of these corporate governance mechanisms on firm performance. We seek to identify the effect of corporate governance mechanisms on firm performance, while considering the conditioning role of capital structure.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1 Theoretical framework

This study integrates three complementary theories: agency theory, resource dependence theory, and trade-off theory. To explain how corporate governance affects firm performance and how capital structure affects this relationship. Agency theory suggests that governance mechanisms are essential for mitigating conflicts between managers and shareholders, thereby enhancing firm value (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Strong firm performance can serve as an indirect signal of reduced agency costs, as it may indicate that managers are acting in alignment with shareholder interests under effective governance structures. Resource dependency theory implies that the board is responsible for obtaining external resources and legitimacy, thereby improving performance (Jeffrey Pfeffer & Gerald Salancik, 1978). With board members, reduce environmental uncertainty and improve corporate performance by leveraging their networks and experience—business performance results from both internal governance efficiency and the board's resource-providing function. Trade-off theory illustrates the importance of capital

structure in influencing financial outcomes by explaining how businesses weigh the advantages of debt, such as tax shelters, against its disadvantages, such as bankruptcy risk (Kraus & Litzenberger, 1973). According to the theory, businesses aim to maintain an optimal capital structure that minimizes the weighted average cost of capital and maximizes firm value. According to this paradigm, governance processes indirectly affect business value by either promoting conservative debt levels or intensifying risk-taking behaviours. Consequently, trade-off theory provides a basis for understanding capital structure as a moderating mechanism through which corporate governance influences financial performance.

2.2. Impact of corporate governance on firm performance.

Many empirical studies examine the effect of a firm's corporate governance quality on its shareholders' value. As a proxy for corporate governance quality, researchers use various governance indices. These indices typically aggregate various governance attributes—such as board independence, ownership concentration, and shareholder rights. However, most indices show that shareholder returns and corporate governance quality are positively correlated. The size of a company's board of directors indicates the number of board members. Board size, or the number of board members, is a commonly used metric for assessing the quality of corporate governance.

Corporate boards are among the most important components of corporate governance. A substantial body of literature has examined the relationship between board characteristics and firm performance, as well as the extent to which firm-specific and environmental factors shape the effectiveness of board structures (Coles et al., 2008; Yermack, 1996). These studies suggest that board attributes such as size, independence, and leadership structure affect firm performance by shaping the board's monitoring capacity, advisory role, and access to external resources. However, the impact of these governance mechanisms is not uniform across firms. Instead, their effectiveness depends on organizational complexity, strategic needs, and the broader economic environment.

The agency assumption holds that larger boards are less effective than smaller ones due to coordination and free-riding problems among directors (Jensen, 1993). Large boards may face coordination issues, diluted accountability, and delayed decision-making, thereby compromising monitoring. Thus, a large board is considered an example of agency conflict between control and ownership (Aggarwal et al., 2012). As a result, smaller boards are believed to be more cohesive and productive, thereby enhancing business performance by reducing agency costs. This suggests that smaller boards are more suited for monitoring and advising. In contrast to agency theory,

resource-dependent theory holds that larger boards offer management greater guidance and stronger environmental ties to protect vital resources. To improve the company's access to outside resources, industry expertise, and business relationships (Jeffrey Pfeffer & Gerald Salancik, 1978). In addition to providing credibility, board members can serve as intermediaries among key stakeholders, lenders, and regulators. Accordingly, the impact of board size on company performance may differ based on whether the board's resource-provision function or monitoring role is more important in a particular institutional setting. Prior empirical studies present conflicting views on the relationship between board size and firm performance. More specifically, a body of research finds a positive relationship between board size and firm performance (Coleman & Wu, 2021; Goel et al., 2022). One stream finds a negative relationship (Guest, 2009; Guney et al., 2020). These conflicting findings demonstrate the complex impact of board size on firm performance, as well as the need to address the interrelationships among different, and possibly alternative, corporate governance mechanisms. The above explanation shows that, while the two theories differ in key respects, reconciling them indicates that board size should be determined by market conditions and a firm's fundamentals. In the same vein, the trade-off between the costs and advantages of having a big or small board of directors is determined by the characteristics of the business. Previous research has applied both agency and stewardship theories to examine the impact of CEO duality on shareholder wealth. According to agency theory, CEO duality encourages managerial entrenchment by reducing the board's monitoring efficacy and consequently increasing agency costs. This demonstrates that established CEOs are inclined to promote their interests, rather than maximize shareholder profit. Due to CEO duality, the board's ability to oversee and discipline the CEO is weakened, thereby undermining its independence. The concentration of authority increases the likelihood of managerial entrenchment, allowing self-serving behaviour to persist unchecked, ultimately leading to higher agency costs and lower firm value (Fama & Jensen, 1983; Jensen & Meckling, 1976).

On the other hand, stewardship theory holds that having a CEO and a chairman enhances the company's ability to respond to external factors and maintain a specific strategy. It contends that holding two leadership positions may increase organizational effectiveness by promoting unified command, faster decision-making, and a clearer strategic vision. This perspective views the CEO as a reliable steward who acts in shareholders' best interests rather than as a self-serving individual. Contextual factors such as ownership structure, institutional setting, and business size often influence the empirical data, yet the results remain inconsistent (Davis et al., 1997).

Resource dependency theory proposes that a contingency perspective can reconcile the conflicting perspectives of stewardship theory and agency, thereby addressing CEO duality. In dynamic or resource-constrained situations, the benefits of duality—such as unified leadership and speedier decision-making—may offset the agency-related costs associated with lower board independence. CEO duality improves performance in some industrial settings, such as those characterized by resource scarcity or high complexity (Boyd, 1995; FINKELSTEIN & D'AVENI, 1994). Recent research offers a more nuanced view of CEO duality, the combination of the CEO and board chair roles. Traditional agency theory sees this as a threat to board independence and shareholder value. Scholars contend that CEO duality can improve company performance by offering united leadership, clear strategic direction, and quicker decision-making, drawing on stewardship theory (Donaldson & Davis, 1991). This viewpoint is further supported by resource dependency theory, which underscores the CEO's responsibility for overseeing external relationships and safeguarding vital resources, particularly in unpredictable or changing environments (Boyd, 1995). Empirical studies increasingly suggest that the effectiveness of CEO duality is contingent on context. For example, CEO duality has been found to positively influence firm performance during the growth stage in Vietnamese firms, where leadership concentration facilitates strategic agility (Huy Pham et al., 2020). Wijethilake & Ekanayake (2020) observe a positive effect of CEO duality. They contended that the broader governance framework, particularly the presence of informal CEO authority and the extent of board involvement in strategic decision-making, profoundly affects the impact of CEO duality on business performance. Therefore, the interplay between formal role structure (duality) and informal dynamics of power and board engagement underscores the need for a contingency approach, recognizing that the efficacy of CEO duality is contingent not only on role configuration but also on the allocation and use of power within the governance system. On the other hand, CEO duality reduces accountability procedures, decreases transparency, and increases the likelihood of managerial entrenchment by eliminating the separation between executive management and monitoring. These factors can eventually depress shareholder value. In situations where board independence is poor, ownership is distributed, or institutional governance frameworks are weak, empirical research has repeatedly shown a negative correlation between CEO duality and business success. For example, Mubeen et al. (2021) found that CEO duality is negatively associated with firm performance among Chinese firms.

Board independence is a crucial corporate governance mechanism that enhances the board's ability to oversee management and safeguard shareholders' interests impartially. To improve

supervision and safeguard shareholder interests, agency scholars contend that board independence strengthens the board's monitoring role by lessening management's influence on board decisions. When assessing strategic choices, managerial performance, and financial reporting, independent directors—who are not members of the company's executive team and have no substantial financial or personal connections to management are perceived as operating more responsibly (Fama & Jensen, 1983). Board independence is anticipated to lower agency costs and better align managerial activities with shareholder value maximization by enhancing the board's capacity to monitor and discipline management. Empirical studies yield conflicting results, yet several research studies show that board independence and company performance are positively correlated. For example, empirical evidence from the MENA region indicates that board independence positively affects bank stock performance, suggesting that it is associated with improved performance among MENA banks and highlighting the role of adequate oversight in the region's financial sector (Awad et al., 2024). Along the same lines, research in the Nigerian emerging market environment demonstrates that board independence positively influences firm performance. Across several industries, independent directors repeatedly demonstrate that they improve financial performance metrics, such as Return on Assets (ROA) and Tobin's Q, by strengthening monitoring and delivering more effective strategic oversight (Akinbode et al., 2025). This supports agency theory's assertion that independent boards may reduce management opportunism and align decisions with shareholder interests, particularly in contexts where external governance systems are inadequate or underdeveloped. Contrary to agency theory, which assumes that independent boards enhance firm performance by improving oversight, some studies indicate that board independence has no significant effect, or even a negative one, especially when independent directors lack firm-specific knowledge or are symbolic rather than active monitors.

Empirical evidence demonstrates that board independence can negatively affect firm performance across various contexts and performance measures. For example, Khan et al. (2024) examined Pakistani non-financial companies between 2003 and 2018. They found that board independence has a substantial negative correlation with financial success, as measured by ROA, ROE, the market-to-book ratio, and Tobin's Q. This might be because independent directors may be unable to evaluate management choices or direct strategy in emerging markets with significant information asymmetry and weak regulatory enforcement, leading to negligible or negative performance effects. Empirical evidence from emerging markets casts doubts on the stated advantages of board independence. In their investigation of companies in an emerging market,

Yasser et al. (2017) discovered a strong inverse link between board independence and company performance. This finding calls into question the traditional agency theory belief that independent directors improve supervision and safeguard shareholder interests. Instead, the authors contend that independent directors may lack the power, knowledge, or incentives to contribute effectively to governance in developing markets, where informal interactions, ownership concentration, and regulatory compliance are common. The results corroborate a growing body of research indicating that, rather than improving performance, board independence might occasionally worsen it by creating gaps between board members and operational reality. Although agency theory frequently promotes board independence as a crucial mechanism for enhancing firm performance, several empirical studies indicate no meaningful relationship between board independence and performance. For example, Haldar et al. (2018) found that the number of independent directors and business performance did not significantly correlate, based on an analysis of the impact of board independence on corporate performance in Indian listed corporations. Their results cast doubt on the presumptions of agency theory, which holds that independent directors enhance governance through efficient oversight.

In contemporary corporate governance frameworks, institutional ownership has become a crucial factor in determining a company's performance. There has been considerable academic debate over whether institutional investors improve or limit companies' performance. Agency theory is the primary theoretical foundation for the link between institutional ownership and business performance, as it asserts that institutional investors act as outside agents of oversight to balance management goals with shareholder wealth maximization (Din et al., 2022). Large institutional investors who own significant shares have the opportunity and incentive to closely monitor management decisions, thereby reducing agency costs arising from the separation of ownership and control (Elyasiani et al., 2017). In earlier research, institutional ownership was conceptualized as a corporate governance tool within the agency theory framework. According to agency theory, institutional ownership reduces agency costs and improves performance by aligning management and shareholder interests (Shleifer & Vishny, 1986). This demonstrates how institutional investors can act as effective monitors, exerting pressure on management to act in shareholders' best interests while preventing opportunistic conduct. Their substantial ownership positions and access to business-specific information increase their capacity to influence strategic choices, thereby enhancing firm performance and governance quality. Rather than eliminating residual loss, institutional ownership primarily reduces bonding and monitoring costs. The inherent problems of agency associations, which are difficult to address thoroughly,

make perfect alignment unattainable. Instead of eliminating agency costs, the alignment advantage of institutional ownership is an improvement in the cost-benefit trade-off of managing management opportunism (Din et al., 2022). Furthermore, institutional ownership improves business performance through strengthening management control, not as a goal in and of itself. More efficient monitoring is enabled by concentrated institutional ownership, which enhances alignment between managerial decisions and shareholders' interests. Ultimately, by reducing agency costs and enabling more efficient capital allocation, this alignment enhances company performance. The causal pathway is institutional ownership, increased monitoring, better alignment, better capital allocation, and improved company performance. The fundamental logic of agency theory, which holds that ownership structure affects governance effectiveness by altering the incentives and constraints managers face, is reflected in this sequence. For this reason, scholars highlight institutional ownership as an important corporate governance mechanism that enhances monitoring effectiveness, reduces managerial opportunism, and aligns managerial decisions with shareholder interests, thereby improving firm performance (Cornett et al., 2007; Shleifer & Vishny, 1986). For instance, a study conducted across 22 emerging economies found that institutional ownership improves company performance, as evidenced by Return on Assets (ROA) and Tobin's Q. The scope of this cross-national investigation supports the generalizability of agency theory predictions in developing economies by indicating that institutional investors' monitoring advantages transcend national contexts (Bilyay-Erdogan & Öztürkkal, 2023). Alrwabdah & Lok (2024) reveal similar findings based on a sample of 158 Jordanian firms. Effective governance practices enhance investor confidence and firm valuation, as evidenced by the empirical finding that companies with stronger shareholder rights typically have higher firm values. The results from Jordan, however, show a more complex relationship: although institutional ownership was positively correlated with Tobin's Q, indicating positive market perceptions, it had no discernible effect on Return on Assets (ROA), indicating that in some emerging market contexts, institutional investors may have a greater impact on market value than operational performance. In contrast, empirical evidence demonstrates that institutional ownership can negatively affect firm performance across multiple contexts and performance metrics. This synthesis reveals the contingencies and conditions under which institutional ownership relationships reverse direction. According to a recent study on ASEAN banking companies conducted between 2019 and 2023, institutional ownership significantly impairs company performance. According to the study, institutional ownership is associated with lower profitability. These findings imply that institutional investors may lack the power or

knowledge to improve performance (Luana et al., 2024). Institutional ownership may have positive or negative effects on a firm's performance, depending on the context, as discussed above. Differences in investor types, governance frameworks, and regulatory systems influence the effectiveness of institutional investors as monitors.

H1. Corporate governance is significantly associated with firm performance in GCC firms.

2.3 Impact of Capital Structure on Firm Performance

Firm performance is affected by a firm's capital structure choice. Subject to the firm's creditworthiness and apparent cash flow consistency, a company will inevitably drift toward a capital structure that lowers the cost of capital and increases firm value. The key to optimizing a company's value is to have the optimal capital structure, which combines debt and equity financing to reduce the cost of capital (Myers, 2001). By efficiently managing debt and equity costs, a company can reduce its overall cost of capital and maximize profitability and shareholder value. Therefore, optimizing shareholder value by reducing capital acquisition costs and improving financial asset management is the primary objective of an ideal capital structure (Zhou et al., 2016).

Scholarly interest in the relationship between capital structure and business performance has grown, especially in emerging economies, where institutional constraints often shape financing decisions. Previous empirical analyses of corporate financing structures were used to evaluate popular theories of capital structure, either confirming or disputing them. Agency theory holds that debt can serve as a disciplinary tool, reducing agency costs by restricting management discretion and ensuring the efficient allocation of free cash flows. Insufficient debt would encourage management and stockholders to take unwarranted risks or make less-than-ideal investments. Excessive leverage can lead to wasteful expenditure when free cash flows are high. Firms without robust safeguards against self-serving management may be particularly vulnerable to this impact. Short-term debt can be the most attractive source of external financing when agency costs are high. Therefore, leverage's advantages and agency costs are also significant factors that influence capital structure (Jensen, 1986). The trade-off theory of capital structure provides a robust foundation for understanding how organizations' financing decisions affect their financial performance. This theory posits that organizations seek to establish an optimal capital structure by balancing the advantages of debt financing, such as tax shielding, with the associated costs, including financial distress, bankruptcy risk, and diminished operational flexibility (Kraus & Litzenberger, 1973). Several empirical studies have examined the relationship between capital structure and company performance, with frequently context-

specific results. In Vietnam, Nguyen & Nguyen (2020) investigated listed enterprises and discovered that capital structure had a statistically significant negative influence on company performance. Their findings suggest that increasing leverage reduces profitability, most likely owing to increased financial risk and operational flexibility. This implies that excessive debt may erode rather than enhance business value in emerging markets such as Vietnam, where capital markets remain underdeveloped and corporate governance norms may differ. Yapa Abeywardhana (2016) examines the capital structure and firm performance of UK firms. The study's findings show a strong inverse relationship between leverage and business performance, suggesting that higher debt levels are associated with lower financial efficiency and profitability. In contrast, empirical studies have documented a positive relationship between financial leverage and firm performance, suggesting that moderate debt use can enhance profitability through tax benefits and improved managerial efficiency. Debt finance allows firms to pursue innovative activities and access the resources needed to support their growth (Dakua, 2019; Zhang et al., 2019). These results are consistent with trade-off theory, which supports weighing the advantages of debt against financial risk, and agency theory, which suggests that debt lowers agency costs by restricting the free cash flow available for management exploitation. While corporate governance mechanisms such as board independence, ownership concentration, and institutional ownership have been widely studied for their impact on firm performance, emerging evidence suggests that this relationship may not be uniform across firms with different financial structures. Specifically, leverage may act as a moderating variable, either amplifying or weakening the effectiveness of governance mechanisms. From an agency theory perspective, debt introduces financial discipline by constraining managerial discretion and reducing free cash flow, thereby potentially substituting or complementing internal governance controls (Jensen, 1986). Therefore, the effectiveness of governance mechanisms may depend on a firm's capital structure. Nonetheless, the empirical literature offers scant insight into how leverage shapes the governance–performance relationship, particularly in emerging economies characterized by underdeveloped capital markets and financing decisions influenced by institutional and ownership structures. Our study aims to fill this gap in the literature by examining the moderating role of leverage in the relationship between corporate governance and firm performance in GCC countries, where the interplay between governance and financial structure remains under-researched.

H2. Capital structure moderates the relationship between corporate governance and firm performance in GCC firms.

3. DATA AND RESEARCH DESIGN

3.1 Data

The study utilises data on non-financial companies in GCC countries. This study covers five GCC countries: Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, Kuwait, Oman, and Qatar. The rationale for selecting these specific stock exchanges is the similarity of these countries' economic structures, emerging capital markets, and ongoing corporate governance reforms. These countries share characteristics such as high ownership concentration, state- or family-controlled firms, and stock exchanges that are increasingly aligned with international regulatory standards. Their shared regional context and levels of governance enforcement make them suitable for examining how leverage moderates the corporate governance–performance relationship. All five countries have introduced or enhanced corporate governance frameworks aligned with OECD principles. The data was compiled from multiple databases. The financial statements of firms are available from three primary sources: the official websites of their respective stock exchanges, the Thomson Reuters Eikon database (Refinitiv), and the annual reports of GCC companies. Some corporate governance data were collected manually from firms' CG and annual reports. The sampling period is 8 years, covering 2016 to 2023. The final sample consisted of a panel data set of 133 non-financial firms, yielding 1064 observations.

3.2. Variables

Firm performance can be measured using various operational and financial indicators, each capturing different dimensions of a firm's outcomes. Return on equity, operating margins, and cash flow ratios are among the most common ways the literature measures performance. This research selects Return on Assets (ROA) and Tobin's Q as the principal metrics for evaluating firm performance. ROA is a favourable measure of operational performance because it shows how effectively a company uses its assets to generate profit. Tobin's Q, on the other hand, measures market-based performance by comparing a company's market value to its assets. Together, these two metrics provide a balanced view that links accounting- and market-based performance dimensions.

Regarding corporate governance (CG), capital structure, and control variables, we consider incorporating various board-level attributes as indicators of governance quality, specifically board size, board independence, CEO duality, and institutional ownership. Previous governance literature extensively employs these variables to evaluate the efficacy of monitoring and

managerial accountability. To isolate the effect of governance mechanisms on firm performance, leverage, measured as the ratio of total debt to total assets, is also introduced as a moderating variable. The study investigates whether leverage moderates the relationship between corporate governance and firm performance by incorporating interaction terms between CG variables and leverage in the regression model. This approach allows testing whether the impact of governance on performance varies with the firm's capital structure. The model controls for relevant firm-specific characteristics, including firm size, age, and sales growth, as these factors may independently influence performance.

Table 1. Variable definitions.

Variable code	Variable name	Variable description
BD_SIZE	Board size.	Number of board directors, including a chairperson and independent directors.
BD_IND	Board independence	The ratio of the number of independent directors to the number of all directors.
CEO_DUAL	CEO duality	CEO duality is a dummy variable that equals one if the CEO is also the board chair and zero otherwise.
InstOwn	Institutional ownership %	Cumulated percentage of shares held by institutional investors (5% rule).
ROA	Return on assets	The ratio of earnings before interest and taxes to total assets.
Tobin Q	Tobin's Q	The ratio of the market value of equity.
LEV	Financial leverage	The ratio of total debt to total assets.
lnFage	Firm age	The natural logarithm of the number of years since the firm's listing.

InFsize	Firm size	The natural logarithm of total assets.
InSG	Sales Growth	Sales t – Sales t-1 / Sales t-1
Year dummies	Year dummies	An eight-year dummy for each of the years from 2016 to 2023.

By: The Author

3.3. Research methodology

This study employs a two-step dynamic System Generalized Method of Moments (System GMM) approach to examine the effect of corporate governance on firm performance and to evaluate the moderating role of leverage in this relationship, using panel data from 133 firms over the period 2016 to 2023. The two-step GMM estimator is employed in the study to address potential endogeneity. Measurement errors, omitted-variable bias, or a reverse causal relationship between capital structure and company performance may all contribute to endogeneity (Wintoki et al., 2012). The two-step system GMM, developed by Arellano and Bond (Blundell & Bond, (1998). It is well-suited to dynamic panel data. Lagged levels of the variables serve as internal mechanisms to mitigate simultaneity bias and unobserved heterogeneity. By accounting for autocorrelation and heteroskedasticity, the two-step process increases efficiency. It yields a reliable standard. The study ensures the reliability and consistency of the estimated association between capital structure and financial performance by integrating multiple approaches.

3.4. Model estimation

The following panel data model is estimated.

To test the hypotheses in this study, we analysed the data from two perspectives. In the first scenario, we investigate the impact of corporate governance on firm performance, controlling for firm characteristics. The following baseline model is specified:

$$ROA_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 ROA_{it-1} + \beta_2 InstOwn_{it} + \beta_3 lnBsize_{it} + \beta_4 Ceo_{it} + \beta_5 Ind_{it} + \beta_6 lnFsize_{it} + \beta_7 lnSG_{it} + \beta_8 lnFage_{it} + year\ dummies + \eta_t + \epsilon_{it}$$

$$Tobin\ Q_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Tobin\ Q_{it-1} + \beta_2 InstOwn_{it} + \beta_3 lnBsize_{it} + \beta_4 Ceo_{it} + \beta_5 Ind_{it} + \beta_6 lnFsize_{it} + \beta_7 lnSG_{it} + \beta_8 lnFage_{it} + year\ dummies + \eta_t + \epsilon_{it}$$

Equation (1)

From a second perspective, we extend the baseline model by incorporating leverage as a moderating variable to examine whether a firm's capital structure moderates the relationship

between corporate governance mechanisms and firm performance. This is achieved by introducing interaction terms between leverage and each corporate governance variable. The modified model is specified as follows:

$$ROA_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 ROA_{it-1} + \beta_2 InstOwn_{it} + \beta_3 lnBsize_{it} + \beta_4 Ceo_{it} + \beta_5 Ind_{it} + \gamma_1 Lev_{it} + \delta_1 (CG \times Lev_{it}) + \beta_6 lnFsize_{it} + \beta_7 lnSG_{it} + \beta_8 lnFage_{it} + year\ dummies + \eta_t + \epsilon_{it}$$

$$Tobin\ Q_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Tobin\ Q_{it-1} + \beta_2 InstOwn_{it} + \beta_3 lnBsize_{it} + \beta_4 Ceo_{it} + \beta_5 Ind_{it} + \gamma_1 Lev_{it} + \delta_1 (CG \times Lev_{it}) + \beta_6 lnFsize_{it} + \beta_7 lnSG_{it} + \beta_8 lnFage_{it} + year\ dummies + \eta_t + \epsilon_{it}$$

Equation (2)

4. EMPIRICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Descriptive statistics

Table 2 presents descriptive statistics for the variables examined in the study. The mean ROA is 0.062, indicating that, on average, the companies in the sample performed well financially, earning a 6.2% return on their assets during the study period. This means management is effectively using the resources they have to create value, ensuring a fair return for various stakeholders. The average Tobin's Q is 1.326, indicating that the market values companies more than their book value. This phenomenon may be due to investors' belief that the company will generate substantial future profits, possess valuable intangible assets, or have a strong management team, all of which contribute to the company's high market value. The average leverage ratio is 0.260, meaning that approximately 26% of a firm's assets are financed by debt. This indicates moderate use of financial leverage, reflecting firms' financing strategies and risk preferences. Also, the CEO's average is 0.065, indicating that the CEO chairs the board in 6.5% of companies. According to best governance practices, this comparatively low proportion suggests that most of the sample's companies maintain distinct executive and board leadership positions. Additionally, the average score of 42.529 indicates that about 42.5% of board members are independent directors across the companies in the study. This indicates a somewhat independent board, often associated with improved supervision, reduced management entrenchment, and enhanced corporate governance. Similarly, the average board size is eight members, indicating that most companies have boards neither too big nor too small. This might help them make excellent decisions while still having a wide range of skills. Institutional investors own, on average, 80.6% of the company's shares, indicating they are a powerful presence and may improve corporate governance oversight. Besides, the average business size is 14,305, indicating that most enterprises in the sample are large. Most of the businesses in the

sample are well-established and mature, with an average age of 30.5 years. The average sales increase is 12.8%, indicating that companies are making a moderate amount of money each year, but there is significant diversity within the sample.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of the study variables

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
ROA	1064	.062	.076	-.423	.515
Tobin Q	1064	1.326	1.068	-.074	13.587
Lev	1064	.26	.171	0	.72
CEOD	1064	.065	.246	0	1
IND	1064	42.529	24.106	0	100
InstOwn	1064	.806	.395	0	1
BSIZE	1064	8.001	2.247	1	25
Fsize	1064	14.305	1.437	9.298	18.709
Fage	1064	3.053	.611	0	4.189
Sg	1064	.128	1.156	-.98	35.121

Note: This table presents a summary of the descriptive statistics for the research key variables in their original form.

4.2 Correlation analysis

Table 3 displays the correlation matrix, which illustrates the relationships among all variables. There is a significant correlation between ROA and Tobin's Q, suggesting that firms with higher profitability are more highly valued in the market. Both ROA and Tobin's Q negatively correlate with leverage. CEO duality is also negatively associated with performance, supporting the idea that separating leadership from the board strengthens governance. There is a positive relationship between board size and company size. There is a positive relationship between firm size and institutional ownership, suggesting that larger companies attract more institutional investors. These patterns are consistent with theoretical expectations and provide a preliminary view of how firm characteristics and governance mechanisms are interrelated.

We assess the robustness of the System Generalized Method of Moments (System GMM) estimations using several standard diagnostic tests. The Arellano-Bond test for first-order autocorrelation AR (1) was statistically significant, as expected, while the second-order autocorrelation test AR (2) was not significant, confirming the absence of serial correlation in the differenced residuals. This supports the validity of the model's moment conditions. In addition, the Hansen J-test of overidentifying restrictions was not significant, indicating that the

instruments used are valid and uncorrelated with the error term. Together, these results suggest that the GMM estimators are correctly specified and that the instruments are appropriate for addressing endogeneity in the panel-data context. Furthermore, all financial variables are winsorized at the 1% level to mitigate the impact of outliers.

Table 3: Correlation matrix

Variables	ROA	Tobin Q	Lev	CEOD	IND	InstOwn	BSIZE	lfsize	lfage	Sg
(1) ROA	1.000									
(2) Tobin Q	0.458 (0.000)	1.000								
(3) Lev	-0.269 (0.000)	-0.079 (0.010)	1.000							
(4) CEOD	-0.101 (0.001)	-0.140 (0.000)	0.069 (0.024)	1.000						
(5) IND	0.046 (0.138)	0.012 (0.689)	-0.160 (0.000)	-0.073 (0.017)	1.000					
(6) InstOwn	0.021 (0.491)	-0.219 (0.000)	-0.103 (0.001)	0.003 (0.910)	0.017 (0.587)	1.000				
(7) BSIZE	0.022 (0.480)	0.030 (0.327)	-0.036 (0.240)	-0.112 (0.000)	0.114 (0.000)	0.106 (0.001)	1.000			
(8) lfsize	-0.071 (0.021)	-0.187 (0.000)	0.112 (0.000)	-0.046 (0.137)	0.068 (0.027)	0.244 (0.000)	0.346 (0.000)	1.000		
(9) lfage	-0.058	-0.062	-0.132	0.057	-0.068	0.017	0.107	0.051	1.000	

	(0.057)	(0.044)	(0.000)	(0.065)	(0.028)	(0.580)	(0.000)	(0.095)		
(10) Sg	-0.007	0.064	-0.015	-0.015	0.033	0.004	-0.032	0.007	0.002	1.000
	(0.816)	(0.038)	(0.634)	(0.624)	(0.277)	(0.892)	(0.299)	(0.815)	(0.946)	

Note: This table presents the correlation matrix.

4.3 Effect of corporate governance on firm performance

Table 4 presents the results of dynamic panel regressions examining the effects of corporate governance on firm performance in GCC countries, using ROA and Tobin's Q as performance measures. Both reveal a strong and statistically significant persistence in firm performance and valuation over time, as shown by the positive coefficients on the lagged dependent variables (ROA: $\beta = 0.778$, $p < 0.01$; Tobin's Q: $\beta = 0.597$, $p < 0.01$). A key finding across both measures is the negative and significant effect of CEO duality on firm performance (ROA: $\beta = -0.013$, $p < 0.05$; Tobin's Q: $\beta = -0.164$, $p < 0.05$), suggesting that combining the roles of CEO and board chair undermines both profitability and market valuation. This result is consistent with those of (Ali et al 2022) and Duru et al., (2016). This supports agency theory arguments for separating leadership roles to strengthen governance and performance in the GCC context (Fama & Jensen, 1983; Jensen & Meckling, 1976).

On the other hand, in Tobin's Q model, board size shows a positive and significant association with firm value ($\beta = 0.171$, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that larger boards may positively affect market perceptions, possibly by enhancing access to expertise or stakeholder networks. However, board size does not have a significant impact on ROA. Our findings are consistent with the recent results of (Agha & Ashogbon, 2025; Omenihu & Nwafor, 2025). This finding also aligns with resource dependence theory, which suggests that larger boards provide access to a broader range of expertise, resources, and external networks, thereby enhancing a firm's legitimacy and strategic positioning in the market (Jeffrey Pfeffer & Gerald Salancik, 1978).

Similarly, the coefficient for institutional ownership is positive and significant in the ROA model ($\beta = 0.009$, $p < 0.10$), suggesting that increased institutional investor involvement is associated with improved firm profitability. However, its effect on market valuation (Tobin's Q) is not statistically significant. Suggesting that institutional investors may be more effective in enhancing internal firm performance than in influencing market valuation. The result is in line with the findings of (Duppati et al., 2023). Thus, hypothesis 1 is supported. Corporate governance is significantly associated with firm performance.

Table 4: GMM estimations.

ROA	ROA	Tobin Q
L.ROA / Tobin Q	0.778***	0.597***
	(0.199)	(0.123)
BFSIZE	-0.001	0.171***
	(0.005)	(0.065)
CEOD	-0.013**	-0.164**
	(0.006)	(0.069)
IND	0.000	-0.000
	(0.000)	(0.000)
Inst Own	0.009*	-0.069
	(0.005)	(0.060)
lnFSIZE	0.001	-0.683***
	(0.009)	(0.247)
lnFAGE	-0.019	-0.029
	(0.024)	(0.077)
lnSG	0.001	-0.006
	(0.001)	(0.011)
Constant	0.050	1.571**
	(0.071)	(0.633)
Year dummies	Yes	Yes
No. of Observations	1064	1064
No. of Firms	133	133
Hansen Prob > Chi Sq.	0.155	0.493
AR (1): P-value	0.000	0.001
AR (2): P-value	0.992	0.738

Note: This table reports empirical results from estimating Eq. (1).

Figures in the parentheses are standard errors.

Asterisks indicate significance at *, $p < 0.1$; **, $p < 0.05$; ***, $p < 0.01$

4.4 The moderating effect of capital structure between corporate governance and firm performance

The results on the moderating effect of capital structure on the relationship between corporate governance and firm performance. Table 5 presents findings on the relationships among CEO duality, board size, board independence, institutional ownership, and firm performance, with a particular focus on the moderating role of capital structure. The results provide evidence about the moderating effect of capital structure on the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and firm performance in selected GCC countries. The findings indicate that the interaction between leverage and CEO duality is statistically significant in both performance models. The interaction is negative in the ROA model, indicating that CEO dualism has a more negative effect on performance in companies with high leverage. In the Tobin Q model, the interaction is positive, suggesting that in firms with higher leverage, the negative impact of CEO duality on firm value is reduced. As a result, even when CEO duality is present, the market may perceive the risk as lower in highly leveraged firms due to the disciplinary role of debt. Likewise, Tripathi et al. (2024). Their study examined the moderating role of capital structure in the relationship between various corporate governance mechanisms and firm value in the Indian context. Their findings show that leverage can alter the strength of the governance-performance relationship, supporting the view that capital structure interacts with internal governance mechanisms to shape firm outcomes. Although their research focused on distinct governance variables, their findings align with the current study's conclusion that the impact of CEO duality on performance depends on the firm's leverage level.

These findings suggest that capital structure plays a conditional role in shaping corporate governance effectiveness. In line with agency theory, higher leverage increases the need for effective governance to control agency costs. A highly leveraged firm's performance reduces more when CEO duality is present. However, for market-based performance (Tobin's Q), leverage may act as a substitute governance mechanism, imposing financial discipline that partially mitigates the governance weaknesses associated with CEO duality. In addition, other interaction terms between leverage and governance variables—such as board size, board independence, and institutional ownership—were not statistically significant relative to the baseline model, which includes only main effects. This indicates that incorporating leverage as a moderator does not augment the explanatory capacity of these governance variables. In contrast, the interaction between leverage and CEO duality remains significant and impactful, indicating that the moderating effect of capital structure is uniquely pronounced when leadership roles are concentrated, reinforcing the importance of separating the CEO and board chair positions in

highly leveraged firms. Thus, hypothesis 2 is supported. Capital structure moderates the relationship between corporate governance and firm performance.

Table 5: GMM estimations.

ROA	ROA	Tobin Q
L.ROA / Tobin Q	1.037***	0.589***
	(0.353)	(0.124)
BSize	0.008	0.171
	(0.015)	(0.302)
CEOD	-0.070*	0.564**
	(0.042)	(0.270)
IND	0.000	-0.000
	(0.000)	(0.000)
Inst Own	0.016	-0.196
	(0.040)	(0.242)
Lev	-0.231	-0.308
	(0.521)	(0.612)
lnFSIZE	0.006	-0.685***
	(0.021)	(0.251)
lnFAGE	0.007	-0.030
	(0.009)	(0.078)
lnSG	0.001*	-0.006
	(0.001)	(0.011)
Constant	-0.027	1.665**
	(0.079)	(0.651)
Year dummies	Yes	Yes
No. of Observations	1064	1064
No. of Firms	133	133
Hansen Prob > Chi Sq.	0.906	0.531
AR (1): P-value	0.000	0.001
AR (2): P-value	0.968	0.728

Note: This table reports empirical results from estimating Eq. (2).

Figures in the parentheses are standard errors.

Asterisks indicate significance at *, $p < 0.1$; **, $p < 0.05$; ***, $p < 0.01$

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we examine the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and firm performance and whether this relationship is moderated by capital structure in the context of publicly listed firms in GCC countries. Using dynamic panel data models and two performance measures, return on assets (ROA) and Tobin's Q, the study provides evidence that governance structures and financial leverage jointly shape firm performance.

In the baseline model, the results indicate that CEO duality has a consistently negative and significant effect on both profitability and firm value, consistent with agency theory, which posits that combining the roles of CEO and board chair undermines board independence and weakens oversight. In contrast, board size has a positive and significant effect on firm value, consistent with resource dependence theory, which posits that larger boards are valuable sources of strategic resources and external linkages. Institutional ownership shows a positive, significant effect on ROA but no significant impact on market valuation, suggesting that institutional investors may contribute more to internal performance than to external market perceptions of the firm.

When the moderating effect of capital structure is introduced, the results indicate that leverage interacts significantly with CEO duality in both models. In the ROA model, the interaction term is negative, indicating that CEO duality worsens in firms with high debt. This reinforces the notion that financial risk amplifies governance weaknesses. However, in the Tobin Q model, the interaction is positive, suggesting that in more leveraged firms, debt may serve as an external disciplining mechanism that mitigates market concerns about concentrated leadership. The interactions between leverage and other governance variables—board size and institutional ownership—were not statistically significant, suggesting that their effects on performance are more direct and stable, regardless of capital structure.

Overall, the study highlights the context-dependent nature of governance effectiveness, showing that the impact of leadership structure and ownership on firm performance varies with financial conditions. These results contribute to the growing body of evidence that capital structure is an essential factor in corporate governance, particularly in emerging markets such as the GCC, where ownership patterns and institutional environments differ from those in developed economies. For policymakers, investors, and corporate boards, the results underscore the

importance of considering both internal governance and financial leverage in efforts to enhance firm performance and resilience

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